

Social Media Influencers' Visual Framing of Chinese Culture on YouTube

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Abstract

The concept of framing is increasingly applied to the analysis of images and provides a significant new direction for the development of theory. However, little prior research has focused on how social media influencers construct Chinese cultural values. This study analyses the metaphors and symbols used by Chinese YouTubers in video narratives by applying a visual framework to determine the presentation that influences viewers' understanding and perception. Using content analysis, this study found that social media influencers (Liziqi) present a visual micro-narrative. At its core, it shares personal experiences and connects to the cultural context and deep-rooted memories of the audience. The cultural exchange of micronarratives can break down nations' arrogance and prejudice, resulting in less hatred and weeping. Such unofficial narratives are essential for a genuine comprehension and recognition of contemporary China. The current study increases our understanding of Chinese culture on YouTube and extends the use of visual framing in cultural communication. Additionally, it facilitates the development of more efficient communication strategies for social media influencers.

Introduction

The Internet has developed into a global and multilingual phenomenon (Danet & Herring, 2003). YouTube (Arthurs et al., 2018), the second most visited site after Google.com, is a new realm of multicultural where a global audience can share experiences, opinions, and collectively watch, evaluate, and interact with others from all over the world (Burke & Snyder, 2008; Lange, 2007; Traynor, 2020). YouTube is seen as a platform for intercultural communication and understanding, enabling people to connect globally. Interactions and relationships with YouTubers from various countries can increase cultural diversity and inclusiveness among audiences.

Based on previous research, YouTubers, known as social media influencers (SMI), can identify the resources they use and the messages they create to influence their audience by overlaying the images they project (Mera et al., 2021; Schwenzow et al., 2021). Notably, the content they produce has become a rich data source for social scientists. This is because of the fact that video on social media has surpassed television as the dominant form of information dissemination (Kretschmer & Peukert, 2020). Furthermore, data indicate that by 2022, more than 80% of interconnected grid traffic will be made up of video (Cisco, 2021). Therefore, YouTuber-generated video content became of interest to this study.

In 2019, a Chinese girl named Liziqi became popular overseas with her videos. At present, she ranks first in the China district of the international social media platform—YouTube, with more than 17.4 million subscribers and 124 videos with over three billion views. According to Deborah et al. (2019), Liziqi is a social media influencer, defined as 'an active and empowered social media user who is listened to and seen as a trusted source by other social media users (p. 9)'. She is a mega influencer with Diamond status in YouTube's partner programme (with over 10 million subscribers) and is highly influential in shaping viewers' opinions and attitudes. In terms of the number of YouTube subscribers, video views, likes, and comments, *Liziqi's* videos have achieved a phenomenal intercultural communication effect on overseas communication platforms.

YouTube contains a lot of entertaining content that brings its audience a lot of relaxation and joy. However, Liziqi cannot just be viewed as merely a channel that provides entertainment for people because she brought the audience with rich Chinese culture and conveyed Chinese values. Presently, little is known about the intentions of social media influencers in promoting Chinese culture in cyberspace. However, this study's investigation may shed light on their intentions and visual frameworks. This study employs framing theory to examine how Liziqi constructs Chinese cultural values to impact multicultural audiences. Answers can be found by interpreting image associations as 'closer to reality' and creating 'stronger and more direct cues' (Rodriguez & Dimitrova, 2011, p. 51). Theoretically, this study provides culture studies scholars with an overview of framing theory, which is widely used in communication research and contributes to our understanding of Chinese culture through the application of visual framing theory, which is rarely applied to videos exploring cultural diffusion. Furthermore, from a practical standpoint, this paper develops a new framework for multicultural audiences on

social media, which could facilitate the creation of more efficient communication strategies for social media influencers.

Theoretical Framework

In the last decade, the concept of frames has been increasingly applied to the analysis of images, and as Coleman puts it, 'visual framing provides an important new direction for theory building and future research'(2009, p. 233). According to Entman, framing is a process of selecting and emphasising certain aspects of perceived reality in textual communication and 'promoting a particular problem definition, causal interpretation, moral evaluation, and/or treatment recommendation'(1993, p. 52). It has two levels: audience framing and news framing. Audience framing is defined as the interpretive schemas or clusters of ideas that guide people's information processing, whereas media framing focuses on the central concept or narrative that gives meaning to an event (Gamson & Modigliani, 1989). This study examines the ways in which YouTube influencers present Chinese culture. The media framework is considered suitable for this research since it defines the message and presentation method presented to the audience (Iyengar, 1991).

The presentation of media content influences the audience's comprehension and perception. Language is an effective means of persuasion, but images are more persuasive because they have the property of 'enhancing or mitigating their consequences' (Messaris & Abraham, 2001, p. 215) or even overriding the information contained within the text (Wischmann, 1987). Images that create more vivid memories than text are more appealing to viewers. And research indicates that visual frames typically usually win in conflict with textual frames (Ferguson, 2000). This is due in part to the fact that the visual effect of images is convincing due to their resemblance to reality and in part to the fact that images have a greater capacity to evoke strong emotions.

Brantner et al. (2011) state that visual framing is 'the selection and emphasis of some aspects of the perceived reality by visual stimuli (p. 525)'. Although visual framing is a highly effective framing tool, identifying them remains challenging. Rodriguez and Dimitrova's (2011) four-tiered model for analysing the visual framework: (1) visuals as denotative systems, (2) visuals as stylistic-semiotic systems, (3) visuals as connotative systems and (4) visuals as ideological representations, provides fundamental guidance. Motahar et al. (2021) investigate how social media influencers employ a four-tiered model to frame Iran as a tourist destination on YouTube. Additionally, the Hijabers constructed their Instagram images primarily through borders, depth of field, reference framework, and titles, revealing global consumer culture and the consumer culture hidden in the middle class (Baulch & Pramiyanti, 2018). The food-themed videos reflect political debates and metaphorical reflections on cultural diversity through culinary practices (Fresno-Calleja, 2013). The Muslim woman image and halal food, unique Islamic visual symbols in Japan's tourism digital brochures, have become important elements in building the image of Japan as a halal destination (Sukmayadi & Effendi, 2020). The above-mentioned literature interprets a good indication of some of the principles of visual framing. However, the framing studies of the last decade have primarily focused on political communication and have lacked research from broader fields such as religion, ethnic culture, and cross-cultural communication. Therefore, this study draws on the visual framing technique that Rodriguez and Dimitrova (2011) proposed to gain insight into social media influencers' construction of Chinese cultural values on YouTube.

The majority of people's knowledge of traditional Chinese culture comes from texts or static artefacts; consequently, they develop a natural sense of awe and estrangement. The transmission of traditional culture does not entail its preservation in its entirety, but rather a process of active selection and interpretation, which has taken on increased significance in the era of social media. This study employs a visual framing to investigate the symbolism of Chinese culture on social media by identifying metaphors, allusions, symbols, and representations in narratives that resonate with multicultural audiences. Visuals as connotative systems and ideological representations are of greater interest to us.

Methodology

Since considering videos may embed multiple meanings and lead to various interpretations, in studying visual content and its impact on viewers, this paper used an interpretative paradigm to reveal the different connotations of visual material based on the polysemantic nature of dynamic images (Mura & Pahlevan Sharif, 2019).

In terms of methodology, this study used an online ethnography approach (Kozinets, 2006) to collect visual materials to explore reality in the online world. Online ethnography is the application of ethnographic principles, perspectives, and methods to virtual or digital environments, with the goal of describing and explaining social, cultural, and communicative phenomena in virtual spaces (Hart, 2017). This is consistent with the ethnographic stance in the interpretive paradigm. We argue that the highly contextualised, descriptive, and interpretive technique of online ethnography lends itself to investigating culture in the social media space and can assist academics in analysing the complicated ways in which culture is formed (Hine, 2000). Hence, this paper scrutinises the data, observes and pays attention to virtual space sites, and then focuses on the videos of social media influencer (Liziqi) on YouTube, an innovative and ground-breaking social media influencer representative who creates videos to spread Chinese culture.

Data collection

The researcher selected the Guinness World Record of the most subscribed Chinese YouTube channel,—Liziqi, as a single case. The reason is that the media has included her intercultural communication in the official discourse of boosting cultural confidence and Chinese cultural soft power: Spreading Chinese culture, telling Chinese stories well, and living the wonderful and confident Chinese people are the vivid inspiration that Liziqi brings to us (Ping, 2019). Evidently, Liziqi has become a representative of China, possessing a distinct national colour and a national cultural identity. She is a symbolic presence (viewed more than 3 billion times on YouTube between 2017 and 2022).

Liziqi created six playlists on her YouTube page, namely, Top videos, Seasonal diet, Chinese festival food, Sound of blooming flowers, Oriental intangible cultural heritage, and Traditional handicraft. The 'Top videos' playlist is a collection of videos with the highest views and likes from the other five playlists. The remaining five playlists were categorised by Liziqi according to the themes of the videos. Based on the five different thematic albums set up by Liziqi on the YouTube channel, the researcher used the purposive sampling method to take one item from each of them as a sample (Table 1).

Table 1. Research samples

No.	Albums	Video titles	Length	Views	Comments	Likes (Around)
1	Seasonal diet	Kumiss and Roasted Whole Lamb 酿一罐子马奶酒再配上滋滋冒油的烤全羊	10'15	13,763,921	16,873	260,000
2	Chinese festival food	Spring Festival dish 福气满满团圆菜，吉祥如意幸福年—年夜饭	10'02	17,936,457	11,670	250,000
3	Sound of blooming flowers	Make a peach blossom crown with silk flowers 用绢花工艺做了套桃花发冠，带上爱人浪了一把春天	19'07	7,959,704	30,920	350,000
4	Oriental intangible cultural heritage	Scholars four treasures—an Epitome of Thousands Years of Chinese Culture (笔墨纸砚)	11'40	14,220,043	17,924	109,000
5	Traditional handicraft	Shu Embroidery 千年民俗蕴服章之美，蜀绣文化彰华夏礼仪	10'25	18,335,869	21,889	420,000

Colour is an analysis unit of this study. In Liziqi's videos, the objects providing colour are abundant, but they can generally be divided into costume and environmental colour. Costume colour reflects the personality and temperament of a particular character and various aspects of cultivation in different degrees. As the form of space on which the characters live, the environmental colour expresses the beauty of the natural scenery and, more importantly, creates the overall colour atmosphere and emotional tone. Analysing the use of colour in Liziqi's videos to explore how the language of colour represents the real world, renders the atmosphere, narrates the story, and evokes the viewer's imagination. The researcher manually recorded the different colours according to the classification of environmental and costume colours, and the frame data were intercepted for further analysis.

Analysis

Content analysis is a method of conveying the author's intent by reading closely, understanding, and interpreting the content of a text (Drisko & Maschi, 2016). This method emphasises truthful, objective, and comprehensive

exploration of the original meaning of textual content and has a certain depth that is suitable for this case study research. In content analysis, data is produced, not found, to answer a phenomenon or a specific question within the context of a particular text. Consequently, the researcher must design a coherent and logical structure for the conducted research project. This design is justified on the one hand by scientific data processing standards and on the other by reference to the contextual background of the text.

First, the researcher made lasting records of transient phenomena, transforming unedited images into analysable representations. Further, the researcher applied Rodriguez and Dimitrova's (2011) visual system to describe the relationships between coded data and phenomena and contexts, exploring ideological representations by inferring the reason behind the visuals portrayed and relying on narrative or discursive conventions to answer and interpret research questions. Notably, the content analysis for this study is not arranged in a linear fashion, and there is no single 'objective approach' to the research design (Krippendorff, 2018, p. 90). Instead, the data are analysed through iterative cycles and repetition of specific processes.

Results

In the videos of Liziqi, the environment colour is the most intuitive visual element for creating a mood and atmosphere. The predominant hues in the videos are red, green, yellow, and blue. The contrast between light and dark, warm and cold environmental colours can evoke a variety of symbolic meanings and feelings. Different colour elements represent implicit meanings in the video.

Red is the colour most readily perceived by the human eye; striking, powerful, and brilliant. In Chinese culture, red represents good fortune, vitality, prosperity, revolution, and politics. On Chinese New Year's Day, Liziqi wore a red sweater representing good fortune, cut out various shapes from red paper, and hand-wrote New Year's wishes on the red paper using a brush (Figure 1). Subsequently, red paper window flowers adhered to the glass of the room; red lanterns were hung under the eaves; red couplets were placed on the door, and red hydrangeas replaced the flowers in the vase (Figure 2). The picture presented a festive, happy, hopeful scene with red as the leading tone. Red's euphoric and auspicious significance was derived from Chinese ancestors venerating sunlight during prayer. Like fire, they believe the red sun can bring infinite hope to families, tribes, and nations. Therefore, red lanterns, red firecrackers, and red couplets were used during the traditional Chinese festival by Liziqi to express beautiful implications and sustenance.

Figure 1. Red couplet **Figure 2. Red lantern**

Red is the colour of fire, powerful and shiny, solemn and noble, and represents the tenacious life that can produce a positive and enterprising attitude. As the family dined on New Year's Eve, Liziqi lit a string of red firecrackers, whose sparks shone brightly in the black night, breaking the silence and illuminating everyone's beaming faces. The flying sparks represent the vigour and tenacity of life and the hope people have for a better future. In Chinese folklore, red is associated with the continuation of life, such as marriage and childbirth. For instance, when hosting a wedding, red lanterns must be hung; red eggs are a gift for the mother of a newborn. In the video, the red light emitted by firecrackers represents the prosperity of life.

In China, red has political connotations. It has positive associations with revolution, progress, and victory and represents faith and justice. From the psychology of primitive ancestors regarding the colour red to the aesthetics of red in folk customs to the red discourse as a political symbol, psychology, historical tradition, and political attributes have achieved a high level of compatibility. This makes red a symbol of national consciousness and emotion in China. Red Tang costumes, red lanterns, and Chinese red knots have become internationally recognised cultural symbols that represent and symbolise China. Through the visual framework created by Liziqi, the colour red is symbolic and representative of China and is abundant with significance.

Another prominent colour in Liziqi's videos is green. Green is the original colour of plants, representing vigour, freshness, and hope. The video of Liziqi was shot in the Bashu region, located in the central-eastern portion of Sichuan Province, China. The topography of this region is a basin surrounded by mountains or plateaus to the west, north, and south, resulting in a typical mountainous landscape. In the land of Bashu, favourable climatic conditions have produced lush vegetation and an abundance of natural resources, and the courtyards of each family are surrounded by green farmland and vegetation. The video showed green courtyards, fields, bamboo forests, mountains, and various green plants that can bring people the tranquillity and harmony of nature.

Petunias are in full bloom along the corner of the wall outside the courtyard on a bright summer day, their vines sprawling haphazardly along the fence and patches of grass, enveloping Liziqi in a verdant atmosphere. Although she appears small in the midst of it, she blends in with the vibrant nature surrounding her (Figure 3). An aura of great power surrounded Liziqi as she sat in a green field in the early spring morning, picking

vegetables while the green field gently glowed in the sunlight (Figure 4). Liziqi's life is surrounded by green, including green vegetables, green fields, green mountains, green bamboo forests, green courtyards, etc., in contrast to the vibrant city life. They symbolise a beautiful environment, good health, and ecological protection, as well as a reflection of the Chinese philosophy of respecting, following, and protecting nature.

Figure 3. Petunia in bloom**Figure 4. Green field**

The colour yellow in the video represented a prosperous harvest and diligence. Yellow is the most brilliant colour in the visible spectrum evoking feelings of contentment, fullness, and warmth in people. It is always associated with the golden autumn season and has a symbolism closely tied to autumn. The video captured the entire growth process of wheat, rice, soybeans, and corn, beginning with the green buds and ending with the yellow fruits. When Liziqi and other farmers harvest vast grain fields, the scene is dominated by a golden yellow hue (Figure 5). After that was completed, only dark yellow land remained. The transformation gave the image a poetic quality, allowed the viewer to appreciate the labour involved in planting, and conveyed the idea that every grain should be valued.

Figure 5. Yellow wheat field

Blue is a calming colour that easily produces the sensation of serenity, peacefulness, profundity, and tranquillity. Whether depicting an indoor setting or a rural landscape, the majority of colours in the Shu embroidery-themed video were blue with a high degree of saturation. The deep colour scheme imbued Shu embroidery with rich cultural connotations and imparted a transcendent and ethereal quality to the environment's beautiful natural scenery, achieving the intended emphasis on the visual mood. The filming of Liziqi took place in Sichuan Province, where the blue hues represented the cold climate at high altitudes. The smoky blue atmosphere resembled a fairytale world on earth, revealing China's distinctive geographical terrain (Figure 6). Using blue tones, Liziqi achieved her original goal for creating the video, which was for the viewer to enjoy idyllic life and natural scenery in their free time and have a calming emotional experience in the hectic and frenetic modern city.

Figure 6. Blue space

The rich colours of the environment created by Liziqi achieve a high level of harmony between the beauty of nature, life, and art, exemplifying the traditional Chinese aesthetics of mood. Traditional Chinese aesthetics is based on the aesthetic relationship between man and nature. Its core concepts are artistic conception,

emphasizing the blending of scenes, the coexistence of reality and reality, and the vitality of the rhythm of life.

The essential mood characteristics portrayed in Liziqi's videos are the 'rhythm of life' and 'natural innocence,' i.e. the inherent beauty of life. The costumes of Liziqi fully reflect colour as an expressive artistic language. She changes the colour and style of her clothing at various times and locations to demonstrate the pursuit of spiritual freedom and liberation. In the video of Kumiss, Liziqi wore a long red cloak and black boots, riding a horse through the mountains and forests with unrestrained joy. After fetching the horse's milk with her Tibetan grandmother, she strolled alone in the mountains and forests. A group of horses was looking for food there, and they were not frightened or dodged by Liziqi's arrival. The long red cloak starkly contrasted with the

predominantly green surroundings (Figure 7), enhancing the image's visual and emotional impact. Behind the appearance of her solitary isolation emanated a potent force: yearning for freedom and searching for her authentic self. Liziqi, wearing a long grey and white cloak (Figure 8), stood atop the mountain and gazed into the distance in the peach blossom-themed video. Snow covered the tree branches beside her, and clouds encircled and flowed around the mountain. The union between Liziqi and the surrounding splendour created a sense of harmony between man and nature.

Figure 7. Long red cloak **Figure 8. White cloak**

Occasionally, Liziqi is dressed in a white Hanfu, lying under Magnolia flowers and enjoying leisure (Figure 9). At times, she turns into a fresh and literary image, wearing a cheongsam in making the plum feast, a dark blue headband, and a white cardigan while handling plums in a garden full of flowers (Figure 10). Most of her clothing was cyan, purplish blue, light blue, dark green, dark red, grey, and other solid colours, which complemented the video's theme. For instance, Liziqi wore a red sweater to prepare the New Year's Eve dinner, echoing the red lanterns, chilli peppers, and firecrackers in the picture. In the spring, she wore a white embroidered silk flower peach blossom Hanfu, which fit the theme of enjoying peach blossoms. In the summer, she primarily wore silk and brocade. However, she wore cotton and linen in the winter with muted hues.

Figure 9. White Hanfu **Figure 10. Blue cheongsam with white cardigan**

When farming, Liziqi wore cotton and linen garments, including grey tube pants, a blue-black cotton linen Chinese-style cloth shirt (Figure 11), and a dark red cotton Tang suit (Figure 12). The clothes were dark and wearable, focusing on functionality without sacrificing comfort. The texture and touch of cotton and linen represented the simplicity of oriental clothing. They resembled those of ancient Chinese folk's coarse-clothed plain clothes. Still, after the redesign, she added many elements of traditional Chinese clothing, such as Chinese-style buttons and a side-opening design with rustic and natural beauty.

Figure 11. Blue-black cotton linen Chinese style cloth shirt

Figure 12. Dark red cotton Tang suit

The various clothing colours symbolise Liziqi's diverse life experiences, attitudes, and values. She initiatively reflects on the relationship between man and nature, man and the world, seeking the essence of life and spiritual belonging in her reflections. She focuses on inner growth and draws from her life experiences as a method for contemplating various cultures. The lifestyle she has is eco-friendly, green, and healthy, exemplifying the ecological concept of man and nature living in harmony and unity, a criticism of developmentalism and consumerism.

Discussion and Conclusion

In recent years, China has actively sought to engage in dialogue on an equal footing with the rest of the world, attempting to share its beautiful vision and high-quality culture with people everywhere. However, 'The Belt and Road Initiative' and 'A Human Community with a Shared Future', as well as the establishment of Confucius Institutes around the world, demonstrate that the values and culture conveyed by China are notably different from what is understood globally. As the creator and planner of the national cultural development policy, the government is primarily responsible for utilising cultural events, international academic communication, and international sporting events to promote the nation's culture and increase its soft power (Nye & Kim, 2019; Wolfe, 2016; Xu et al., 2020). In the era of social media, the discussion environment, communication topics, and cultural diffusion content have all changed significantly.

China's globally famous social media influencers (i.e. Liziqi) on YouTube are attempting to adapt to 'the other.' Although this adaptation is somewhat contingent, it is a strategy of integrating separation and assimilation, which requires cultural confidence to maintain one's own local cultural identity and seeks a common expression between 'me' and 'the other' (Yu & Zhang, 2021). As influential YouTube folk narrators, Chinese social media influencers have the ability to attenuate the prejudices and stigmatization of China resulting from the production of narratives of otherness through their powerful influence and effectively compensate for the limits of government cultural diplomacy.

In this study, social media influencers (Liziqi) utilised the concept of framing theory, which states that the presentation of content influences viewers' understanding of events (Price et al., 1997) to guide subscribers' comprehension of Chinese culture. She constructed a visual framework based on Chinese cultural values, incorporating the concepts of 'harmony between man and nature' and 'individual spiritual freedom.' We are more concerned with how she tells her story truthfully on social media and persuades billions of viewers than with exporting Chinese cultural values.

In the past, Chinese narratives emphasised the Chinese way, Chinese philosophy, Chinese image, and Chinese values (Cai, 2013; Cui, 2017), indicating a solid tendency toward national narratives. Westerners prefer to accept daily, personal and personal and naturally flowing stories. We refer to this kind of story as a 'micro-narrative.' It is evolving into a trending form of expression in the new media era, where the fundamental areas of human life are the entry points for such narratives. The popularity of social media, in particular, is seen as an emerging field of micro-narratives, aiming to tell stories using digital tools and combining text, images, video, and sound (Venditti et al., 2017). The micro-narrative capabilities of social media form an important power for presenting ourselves, comprehending our experiences, and connecting with others (Georgakopoulou, 2022). Through the use of micronarratives, Liziqi and the audience co-create a shared space of meaning. In it, new forms of interaction are created that serve to promote the understanding of Chinese culture.

Liziqi's videos are precisely a visual 'micro-narrative'. At the core of this narrative is sharing personal experience, which connects to the viewer's cultural background and deep-seated memories (Kiss, 2015; Wen, 2021). The emergence of this narrative enables individuals to participate collectively in the construction of stories (Georgakopoulou, 2007), thereby allowing narrators to reach identity through interaction with others (Page et al., 2013). Liziqi incorporated various cultural representations of Chinese elements into the audio-visual language, constructing a symbolic representation of the cultural connotations of Chinese elements through visual symbols. Using figurative cultural representations as the basis for storytelling to achieve cultural communication allows viewers to enter the 'utopia' created by the videos, evoking their collective imagination and memories of a simple, idyllic life, deepening their understanding of Chinese cultural values and philosophy, such as harmony between nature and humanity and individual freedom and liberation.

On the surface, the absence of language was a barrier to communication, but in a cultural field, the ubiquity of symbols diminished language's influence as a single cognitive channel. Videos constitute a low-context cultural

system less dependent on language. This is due to the fact that the visual symbol is capable of cultural conversation across differences, and multimodality further increases the expressive power of dialogic symbols. Multimodal discourse, which combines multiple modal resources such as images, animations, sounds, and colours to convey meaning, has become a popular mode of communication (Venditti et al., 2017). This visually presented content was expressive and permitted the free combination of meanings. Its fluidity and globalism could frequently transcend the barriers of linguistic symbols and provide viewers with more ways to interact with one another.

In a sense, Liziqi, as a social media influencer, expanded the new horizons of foreign communication. Since the COVID-19 epidemic, we have seen human camaraderie across races and nationalities and inflammatory, violent, and discriminatory hate speech. In an information environment rife with lies, competition and pressure began to appear, and groups grew increasingly antagonistic, fragmented, and divided. Liziqi offered a fresh perspective on establishing a productive discussion environment, democratic interaction, and emotional connections for intercultural communication to realize the vision of sharing and resonance. The cultural communication of micronarratives could break down the perceived arrogance and prejudice between nations, leading to less hatred and weeping. Pursuing a universal, humanitarian world ideology is uniquely Chinese in its salvation. This unofficial narrative was crucial for the genuine understanding and recognition of modern China.

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Reference

- Arthurs, J., Drakopoulou, S., & Gandini, A. (2018). Researching YouTube. *Convergence*, 24(1), 3-15. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1354856517737222>
- Baulch, E., & Pramiyanti, A. (2018). Hijabers on instagram: Using visual social media to construct the ideal Muslim woman. *Social Media and Society*, 4(4), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20563051188003>
- Brantner, C., Lobinger, K., & Wetzstein, I. (2011). Effects of visual framing on emotional responses and evaluations of news stories about the gaza conflict 2009. *Journalism and Mass Communication Quarterly*, 88(3), 523-540. <https://doi.org/10.1177/107769901108800304>
- Burke, S. C., & Snyder, S. L. (2008). YouTube: An innovative learning resource for college health education courses. *International Electronic Journal of Health Education*, 11, 39-46.
- Cai, Z. G. (2013). Lun zhongguo dianshiju haiwai chuanbo de celue [On the strategy of overseas dissemination of Chinese TV series]. *South China Television Journal*, (05), 74-77.
- Cisco. (2021). *Cisco Annual Internet Report (2018–2023) White Paper*. Retrieved 26 February from <https://www.cisco.com/c/en/us/solutions/collateral/executive-perspectives/annual-internet-report/white-paper-c11-741490.html>
- Coleman, R. (2009). Framing the pictures in our heads: Exploring the framing and agenda-setting effects of visual images. In *Doing News Framing Analysis: Empirical and Theoretical Perspectives* (pp. 233-261). <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203864463>
- Cui, X. (2017). Shibada yilai “jianghao zhongguo gushi” linian guonei yanjiu zongshu [A review of domestic research on the concept of "telling the Chinese story" since the 18th National Congress]. *International Communications*, (02), 50-52.
- Danet, B., & Herring, S. C. (2003). Introduction: The multilingual internet. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 9(1), JCMC9110. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1083-6101.2003.tb00354.x>
- Deborah, A., Michela, A., & Anna, C. (2019). How to quantify social media influencers: An empirical application at the Teatro alla Scala. *Heliyon*, 5(5), e01677. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2019.e01677>
- Drisko, J. W., & Maschi, T. (2016). *Content analysis*. Oxford University Press.
- Entman, R. M. (1993). Framing: Toward Clarification of a Fractured Paradigm [Article]. *Journal of Communication*, 43(4), 51-58. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-2466.1993.tb01304.x>
- Ferguson, S. D. (2000). *Researching the public opinion environment*. SAGE.
- Fresno-Calleja, P. (2013). Food for thought: Filmic recipes for New Zealand's multiculturalism. *Continuum*, 27(6), 850-861. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10304312.2013.794191>
- Gamson, W. A., & Modigliani, A. (1989). Media discourse and public opinion on nuclear power: A constructionist approach. *American Journal of Sociology*, 95(1), 1-37. <https://doi.org/10.1086/229213>
- Georgakopoulou, A. (2007). *Small stories, interaction and identities* (Vol. 10). John Benjamins Publishing.
- Georgakopoulou, A. (2022). Co-opting small stories on social media: A narrative analysis of the directive of authenticity. *Poetics Today*, 43(2), 265-286. <https://doi.org/10.1215/03335372-9642609>

- Hart, T. (2017). Online ethnography. *The International Encyclopedia of Communication Research Methods*, 1-8.
- Hine, C. (2000). *Virtual ethnography*. Sage.
- Iyengar, S. (1991). *Is anyone responsible? How television frames political issues*. University of Chicago Press.
- Kiss, M. (2015). Film narrative and embodied cognition: The impact of image Schemas on narrative Form. *Embodied Cognition and Cinema*, 43-61.
- Kozinets, R. V. (2006). *Netnography: Redefined* (2nd ed.). Sage.
- Kretschmer, T., & Peukert, C. (2020). Video killed the radio star? Online music videos and recorded music sales. *Information Systems Research*, 31(3), 776-800. <https://doi.org/10.1287/isre.2019.0915>
- Krippendorff, K. (2018). *Content analysis: An introduction to its methodology*. Sage.
- Lange, P. G. (2007). Publicly private and privately public: Social networking on YouTube. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 13(1), 361-380. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1083-6101.2007.00400.x>
- Mera, J. M. B., Miniguano, A. D. E., & Castillo, A. d. R. P. (2021). Marketing of ecuadorian influencers: Effectiveness of content within the YouTube platform. *Revista Publicando*, 8(28), 9-18. <https://doi.org/10.51528/rp.vol8.id2145>
- Messaris, P., & Abraham, L. (2001). The convergence of agenda setting and framing. In *Framing Public Life* (pp. 337-353). Routledge.
- Motahar, P. S., Tavakoli, R., & Mura, P. (2021). Social media influencers' visual framing of Iran on YouTube. *Tourism Recreation Research*, 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02508281.2021.2014252>
- Mura, P., & Pahlevan Sharif, S. (2019). Iran on the news—Exploring videos' effects on potential tourists. *Journal of Tourism and Cultural Change*, 17(2), 208-221. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14766825.2017.1349134>
- Nye, J., & Kim, Y. (2019). Soft power and the Korean Wave. In Y. Kim (Ed.), *South Korean popular culture and North Korea* (1st ed., pp. 41-53). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781351104128>
- Page, R., Harper, R., & Frobenius, M. (2013). From small stories to networked narrative: The evolution of personal narratives in Facebook status updates. *Narrative Inquiry*, 23(1), 192-213. <https://doi.org/10.1075/ni.23.1.10pag>
- Ping, R. (2019, December 30). Zhulao minzu fuxing de jingshen zhizhu [Building a firm spiritual support for national rejuvenation]. *People's Daily*. https://politics.gmw.cn/2019-12/30/content_33438682.htm
- Price, V., Tewksbury, D., & Powers, E. (1997). Switching trains of thought: The impact of news frames on readers' cognitive responses. *Communication Research*, 24(5), 481-506. <https://doi.org/10.1177/009365097024005002>
- Rodriguez, L., & Dimitrova, D. V. (2011). The levels of visual framing. *Journal of Visual Literacy*, 30(1), 48-65. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23796529.2011.11674684>
- Schwenzow, J., Hartmann, J., Schikowsky, A., & Heitmann, M. (2021). Understanding videos at scale: How to extract insights for business research. *Journal of Business Research*, 123, 367-379. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.09.059>
- Sukmayadi, V., & Effendi, R. (2020). Halal destination images of japan: A visual content analysis. *Jurnal Komunikasi: Malaysian Journal of Communication*, 36(3), 312-324. <https://doi.org/10.17576/JKMJC-2020-3603-19>
- Traynor, K. (2020). YouTube: Online video and participatory culture. *European Journal of Communication*, 35(4). <https://doi.org/10.1177/0267323120935319>
- Venditti, S., Piredda, F., & Mattana, W. (2017). Micronarratives as the form of contemporary communication. *The Design Journal*, 20(sup1), S273-S282. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14606925.2017.1352804>
- Wen, Z. H. (2021). Meijiehua shehui de shengming xushi yu qinggan chuanbo: Yi Li Ziqi xianxiang weili [Life narratives and emotional communication in mediated society: The example of Li Ziqi's phenomenon]. *Journal of Taizhou University*, (02), 16-22.
- Wischmann, L. (1987). Dying on the front page: Kent state and the Pulitzer Prize. *Journal of Mass Media Ethics*, 2(2), 67-74. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08900528709358296>
- Wolfe, S. D. (2016). A silver medal project: The partial success of Russia's soft power in Sochi 2014. *Annals of Leisure Research*, 19(4), 481-496. <https://doi.org/10.1080/11745398.2015.1122534>
- Xu, H. G., Wang, K., & Song, Y. M. (2020). Chinese outbound tourism and soft power. *Journal of Policy Research in Tourism, Leisure and Events*, 12(1), 34-49.
- Yu, J., & Zhang, Y. R. (2021). Zhongguo wanghong zai YouTube Zhong de duanshipin kuawenhua chuanbo fenxi—Jiyu shige zhongguo wanghong de duanshipin neirong fenxi [Cross-cultural analysis of Chinese weblebrities' short videos in YouTube—Based on the short video content analysis of ten Chinese weblebrities]. *Southeast Communication*, (05), 77-80.

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